

Psychological components of professional-pedagogical culture

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Abstract

This article discusses the role that psychological culture of class teacher plays in the establishment and maintenance of psychological safety in a modern schoolchild. The problem of protection against psychological abuse within the educational environment of a school is particularly important in the current socio-cultural realm. The article analyzes many pedagogical and psychological studies regarding the problem of psychological education of teachers.

Keywords: psychological culture, psychological safety, class teacher, modern schoolchildren

Today's socio-cultural situation is responsible for many examples of negative impact on the formation of personality traits that external factors make. This increases the need for social, psychological and physical security in otherwise unstable social situation. According to many psychological and sociological studies, large percentage of parents is concerned with their child's safety within the educational environment. Parents are concerned about the way their children feel at school, whether they are accepted, understood, positively regarded, respected and loved regardless of their academic success. But they are even more concerned about destructive effects of psychological or physical abuse and bullying their children get from their peers, older children, and, sometimes, teachers.

It seems very important to study influence of teacher's psychological culture on schoolchildren's psychological safety. It seems even more important to define the alternative educational methods that would foster the development of future teachers' psychological culture. Currently, none of the teacher universities and colleges prepares a future teacher for assuming the position of a class teacher [1], which further widens the gap between a modern teacher's personal and professional qualities, and the requirements of class teacher duties.

For professionally competent, successful and effective realization of their duties, class teachers ought to be familiar with the psychological and pedagogical basics of working with children of specific age, be informed about the latest advancements in forms and methods of educational work, know and use modern educational technologies.

The central element of the class teacher professionalism is his or her professional psychological-pedagogical competence, the understanding of the complexity of personality, ability to analyze interaction of schoolchildren with the world, and manifestations of the schoolchild's interpersonal relations with other people. Thus, the psychological culture can be viewed as a part of psychological and pedagogical competence of a class teacher.

The lack of basic psychological literacy is the main reason for many problems, difficulties, conflicts, stress, and emotional hurt in the life and work of both individuals, and the society as a whole. As noted by I.V. Dubrovina (2000), our society need more psychological knowledge and psychological culture, that facilitates interest in another people, respect for their personalities, and a willingness to understand other people's actions, attitudes, and feelings.

In psychology, there is discernment between directed and undirected influence. The first employs persuasion and suggestion. Here a class teacher seeks to achieve a certain result of the pupils. In contrast, the undirected influence has no any special task, and the educational effect is produced by imitating the behavior of a role-model. The non-verbal means of influence are also of certain importance, because with their help it is easy to express the attitude towards a schoolchild, weaken his or her psychological defense and invade the world of the child's senses. Among these are certain facial expressions, gestures, and expressive means of voice (pitch, rhythm of speech, pauses, laughter, and other), eye contact, and tactile contact.

The choice of an educational strategy or of kind of influence is always left to a teacher. Teachers simply need to remember that "it takes a personality to form a personality, and it takes character to form character". A teacher must be a Person, as it is his of her professional characteristics. Therefore, the development of future teachers' psychological culture that would serve as a mechanism for effective communication, understanding, and communication between people of different nationalities, age, gender, occupation and other characteristics, is the basis of the psychological safety of both modern schoolchildren and the educational environment in general.

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